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<http://www.molmod.info/semantics/pims-ii-examples/benchmark/case-1.ttl>
<http://www.molmod.info/semantics/pims-ii-examples/benchmark/case-2.ttl>
<http://www.molmod.info/semantics/pims-ii-examples/benchmark/case-3.ttl>
<http://www.molmod.info/semantics/pims-ii-examples/benchmark/case-4.ttl>
<http://www.molmod.info/semantics/pims-ii-examples/benchmark/case-5.ttl>

Mereosemiotics: Five scenarios

Inprodat e.V. technical report 2021-B

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Borgo and Kutz [1] recently formulated five benchmark scenarios for foundational ontologies, which will be addressed below. The present ontology PIMS-II (Physicalistic Interpretation of Modelling and Simulation – Interoperability Infrastructure) is an implementation of mereosemiotics [2] variant $P_1I_2M_3S_4$. It is available at <http://www.molmod.info/semantics/pims-ii.ttl> and aligned with the EMMO at <http://www.molmod.info/semantics/emmo-pims-ii-alignment.ttl>. A first-order logic axiomatization of the core parts of this ontology is openly accessible and has been submitted for the FOUST 2021 workshop [3].

CASE 1

“There is a four-legged table made of wood. Sometime later, a leg of the table is replaced. Even later, the table is demolished so it ceases to exist although the wood is still there after the demolition.”

There are three (spatio-)temporal regions¹

$$\rho', \rho'', \rho''' : \text{Item}, \quad (1)$$

temporally arranged as given by $\rho' \hookrightarrow_t \rho'' \hookrightarrow_t \rho'''$. We define the individuals

$$\begin{aligned} o : \text{Item}, & & \text{the wooden table;} \\ o_1, o_2, o_3, o_4, o_5 : \text{Item}, & & \text{five pieces of wood, used as legs;} \\ \tilde{o} : \text{Object}, & & \text{an amount of wood,} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

mereologically arranged as given by

¹Notation: \hookrightarrow_t for temporallyPrecedes, σ for isFusionOf, $\dot{P} \dot{-} \dot{P}$ for overlapsWith, \dot{P} for isProperPartOf, \equiv_t for temporallyCoextendsWith, $\neg(\dot{P} \dot{-} \dot{P})$ for doesNotOverlapWith, $\neg(\equiv_t \dot{P} \dot{-} \dot{P})$ for doesNotTemporallyOverlapWith, and $\equiv_t \dot{P} \dot{-} \dot{P}$ for temporallyOverlapsWith; as supplementary material, see also <http://www.molmod.info/semantics/pims-ii-examples/benchmark/case-1.ttl>.

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{o} \sigma (o \ o_1 \ o_2 \ o_3 \ o_4 \ o_5), & \quad \tilde{o} \text{ is the fusion of the table and the legs;} \\ o_1, o_2, o_3, o_4, o_5 \dot{P}^- \dot{P} o & \quad \text{each of the legs overlaps with the table.} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

The legs have intersections with the three temporal regions, which for $1 \leq i \leq 5$ satisfy

$$\begin{aligned} o'_i, o''_i, o'''_i : \text{Item,} & \quad \text{leg } o_i \text{ initially, after the replacement, and after the demolition;} \\ o'_i \dot{P} o_i, & \quad o'_i \text{ is a proper part of leg } o_i, \\ o'_i \equiv_t \rho', & \quad \text{and it temporally coextends with the region } \rho'; \\ o''_i \dot{P} o_i, & \quad o''_i \text{ is a proper part of leg } o_i, \\ o''_i \equiv_t \rho'', & \quad \text{and it temporally coextends with the region } \rho''; \\ o'''_i \dot{P} o_i, & \quad o'''_i \text{ is a proper part of leg } o_i, \\ o'''_i \equiv_t \rho''', & \quad \text{and it temporally coextends with the region } \rho'''. \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

In the beginning, the corresponding temporal parts of legs o_1 to o_4 are proper parts of o

$$o'_1, o'_2, o'_3, o'_4 \dot{P} o, \quad (5)$$

whereas o'_5 , the initial temporal part of o_5 , does not overlap with the table

$$o'_5 \neg(\dot{P}^- \dot{P}) o. \quad (6)$$

Later, with the fifth leg having replaced the first, this becomes

$$\begin{aligned} o''_2, o''_3, o''_4, o''_5 \dot{P} o, & \quad o''_2 \text{ to } o''_5 \text{ are proper parts of the table;} \\ o''_1 \neg(\dot{P}^- \dot{P}) o, & \quad \text{the item } o''_1 \text{ does not overlap with the table.} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

The table does not temporally overlap with the third region, but the amount of wood does

$$\begin{aligned} o \neg(\equiv_t \dot{P}^- \dot{P}) \rho''', & \quad \text{the table and the region } \rho''' \text{ do not overlap temporally;} \\ \tilde{o} \equiv_t \dot{P}^- \dot{P} \rho''', & \quad \text{the wood and the region } \rho''' \text{ overlap temporally.} \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

CASE 2

“Mr Potter is the teacher of class 2C at Shapism School and resigns at the beginning of the spring break. After the spring break, Mrs Bumblebee replaces Mr Potter as the teacher of 2C. Also, student Mary left the class at the beginning of the break and a new student, John, joins in when the break ends.”

To make the two mid-term changes different from each other, let us for the purpose of illustration assume that in a domain ontology aligned with PIMS-II, a didactic process (e.g., a course or a half-course) is formalized as a CognitiveAction in which the instructor

participates as an agent. Since a cognitive action has *exactly one agent* (interpreter), the instructor for the overall course therefore needs to be a collective object, *e.g.*, a plurality of persons. In other roles, *e.g.*, as attendants, arbitrarily many individuals can participate.

We define the individuals²

$$\begin{array}{ll}
\rho', \rho'' : \text{Item}, & \text{(spatio-)temporal regions of the two half terms;} \\
\kappa, \kappa', \kappa'' : \text{CognitiveAction}, & \text{the overall course and its two parts;} \\
a_B, a_M, a_J, a_P : \text{Person}, & \text{Bumblebee, Mary, John, and Potter;} \\
\hat{a} : \text{Agent, Plurality}, & \text{the instructor of the overall course,} \quad (9)
\end{array}$$

such that

$$\begin{array}{ll}
\kappa \dot{P}^- \kappa', \kappa'', & \kappa' \text{ and } \kappa'' \text{ are two proper parts of the course } \kappa; \\
\kappa' \equiv_t \rho', & \text{the first part temporally coextends with the region } \rho'; \\
\kappa'' \equiv_t \rho'', & \text{the second part temporally coextends with the region } \rho''; \\
\kappa' S^\perp \kappa, & \text{the first half-course is the initial step of } \kappa; \\
\kappa'' S^\top \kappa, & \text{the second half-course is the terminal step of } \kappa; \\
\kappa' \dot{\leftrightarrow} \kappa'', & \text{step } \kappa' \text{ directly precedes step } \kappa''; \\
\rho' \dot{\leftrightarrow}_t \rho'', & \text{the first half term temporally precedes the second one.} \quad (10)
\end{array}$$

For the first part of the course,

$$\begin{array}{ll}
a_M \ddot{P} \kappa', & \text{Mary participates (as an attendant);} \\
a_B \ddot{P}_i \kappa', & \text{Bumblebee participates as the instructor (i.e., interpreter);} \\
a_J, a_P \neg(\dot{P}^- \dot{P}) \kappa', & \text{John and Potter are absent,} \quad (11)
\end{array}$$

and for the second part of the course,

$$\begin{array}{ll}
a_J \ddot{P} \kappa'', & \text{John participates (as an attendant);} \\
a_P \ddot{P}_i \kappa'', & \text{Potter participates as the instructor (i.e., interpreter);} \\
a_B, a_M \neg(\dot{P}^- \dot{P}) \kappa'', & \text{Bumblebee and Mary are absent.} \quad (12)
\end{array}$$

To describe the overall course, it can then be stated that

²Notation: \dot{P}^- for `hasProperPart`, \equiv_t for `temporallyCoextendsWith`, S^\perp for `isInitialStepIn`, S^\top for `isTerminalStepIn`, $\dot{\leftrightarrow}$ for `directlyPrecedesStep`, $\dot{\leftrightarrow}_t$ for `temporallyPrecedes`, \ddot{P} for `isParticipantIn`, \ddot{P}_i for `isInterpreterIn`, $\neg(\dot{P}^- \dot{P})$ for `doesNotOverlapWith`, and \triangleleft_p for `isMemberOfPlurality`. See also <http://www.molmod.info/semantics/pims-ii-examples/benchmark/case-2.ttl> as supplementary material.

$$\begin{array}{ll}
a_M, a_J \overset{\cdot}{\dot{P}} \kappa, & \text{Mary and John attended (if 50\% attendance counts);} \\
\hat{a} \overset{\cdot}{\dot{P}}_t \kappa, & \text{the teacher was } \hat{a}, \text{ a plurality (i.e., a collective);} \\
a_B, a_P \prec_p \hat{a}, & \text{Bumblebee and Potter are members of } \hat{a}. \quad (13)
\end{array}$$

CASE 3

First part: Case 3a

“A flower is red in the summer. As time passes, the colour changes. In autumn the flower is brown.”

We define the individuals³

$$\begin{array}{ll}
o : \text{Item}, & \text{the flower;} \\
p : \text{Property}, & \text{the property } \textit{colour}; \\
\ell_1, \ell_2 : \text{Value}, & \textit{red colour} \text{ and } \textit{brown colour}; \\
\rho_1, \rho_2 : \text{Item}, & \text{summer and autumn (of a given year);} \\
\pi_1, \pi_2 : \text{Observation}, & \text{two observation processes;} \\
d_1, d_2 : \text{Assignment}, & \text{data collected by observation,} \quad (14)
\end{array}$$

such that summer temporally precedes autumn, $\rho_1 \hookrightarrow_t \rho_2$. The colour of the flower is observed twice, once in summer and once in autumn:

$$\begin{array}{ll}
\pi_1 \equiv_t \overset{\cdot}{\dot{P}} \rho_1, & \text{the first observation is done in summer;} \\
\pi_2 \equiv_t \overset{\cdot}{\dot{P}} \rho_2, & \text{the second observation is done in autumn;} \\
o \overset{\cdot}{\ddot{E}}_{\text{obs}} \pi_1, \pi_2, & o \text{ is the observed object, i.e., the second triadic element;} \\
p \overset{\cdot}{\ddot{R}} \pi_1, \pi_2, & p \text{ is the target property, i.e., the aim of the observation.} \quad (15)
\end{array}$$

First it is found to be red, and then it is found to be brown:

$$\begin{array}{ll}
\ell_1, \ell_2 \overset{\cdot}{\ddot{D}} p, & \textit{red colour} \text{ and } \textit{brown colour} \text{ are admissible values for } \textit{colour}; \\
d_1 \overset{\cdot}{\ddot{E}}_{\text{obs}} \pi_1, & \text{the outcome (i.e., interpretant) of the first observation is } d_1;
\end{array}$$

³Notation: \hookrightarrow_t for temporallyPrecedes, $\equiv_t \overset{\cdot}{\dot{P}}$ for isTemporallyIncludedIn, $\overset{\cdot}{\ddot{E}}_{\text{obs}}$ for isObservedIn, $\overset{\cdot}{\ddot{R}}$ for isTargetPropertyIn, $\overset{\cdot}{\ddot{D}}$ for isAdmissibleValueFor, $\overset{\cdot}{\ddot{E}}_{\text{obs}}$ for isObservationOutcomeIn, R_D for isAssignmentFor, $\overset{\cdot}{\ddot{D}}$ for isVariableInAssignment, $\overset{\cdot}{\ddot{D}}$ for isValueInAssignment, λ for isLiterally, \prec_p for isMemberOfPlurality, \leftrightarrow for directlyGrounds, S for isStepIn, S^\perp for isInitialStepIn, S^\top for isTerminalStepIn, $\overset{\cdot}{\dot{P}}_t$ for isInterpreterIn, R_α for isAimIn, $\overset{\cdot}{\dot{C}}$ for isSemioticallyConstitutiveOf, $\overset{\cdot}{\dot{P}}_{\text{tool}}$ for isToolIn, $\overset{\cdot}{\dot{P}}$ for isProperPartOf, $\overset{\cdot}{\ddot{E}}_{\text{obs}}$ for isObservationInputIn, $\overset{\cdot}{\ddot{R}}$ for describesMethodAppliedIn, 3 for isTriadOf, $\overset{\cdot}{\ddot{E}}_{\text{ptw}}$ for isOldReferentInPartToWhole, $\overset{\cdot}{\ddot{E}}_{\text{ptw}}$ for changesReferentInPartToWhole, and $\overset{\cdot}{\ddot{E}}_{\text{ptw}}$ for isNewReferentInPartToWhole; cf. <http://www.molmod.info/semantics/pims-ii-examples/benchmark/case-3.ttl> as supplementary material.

$d_2 \ddot{E}_{\text{obs}} \pi_2$, the outcome (*i.e.*, interpretant) of the second observation is d_2 ;
 $d_1, d_2 \text{R}_D o$, the data items d_1 and d_2 both refer to the flower o ,
 $p \dot{D} d_1, d_2$, and they both assign a value to *colour*;
 $\ell_1 \ddot{D} d_1$, in the first case, it is *red colour*,
 $\ell_2 \ddot{D} d_2$, and in the second case, it is *brown colour*.

Second part: Case 3b

“A man is walking when suddenly he starts walking faster and then breaks into a run.”

The original formulation of the problem, given above, sounds informal and would invite a rather straightforward description.⁴ To make the case more relevant to metadata standardization for research data infrastructures⁵ such as NFDI4Cat [4] and NFDI4Ing [5], let us reformulate it such that an Observation takes place and research data are generated.

“To support urban planning, the city administration has installed a video camera and processing equipment in a pedestrian zone to anonymously collect and evaluate movement patterns. Whenever a person enters the field of view of the camera, and until leaving the field of view, the velocity (in the direction of the road) is evaluated over time and ingested into a repository as a data set. Now, a man is walking . . . , etc.”

Individuals are given as follows:

a : Agent, the city administration;
 φ : Proposition, overarching objective concerning urban planning;
 κ : CognitiveAction, a cognitive action consisting of three steps:
 π : Observation, an observation (done with the video camera);
 ι : Interpretation, video processing (done computationally);
 μ : PartToWhole, part-to-whole synecdoche (*i.e.*, a metonymization);
 e, e' : Item, employed equipment: A camera and a computer;
 ℓ : Lexeme, method for the first step, where $\ell \lambda$ “video recording”;
 o, s : Item, a man, and a visual signal of the man;
 o' : Plurality, all the people in the pedestrian zone, such that $o \triangleleft_p o'$;
 s', s'' : Dataltem, a video of the man, and a velocity-over-time data set;
 v, t, ℓ' : Property, velocity, time, and velocity over time, (16)

where the order of the three steps is given by $\pi \leftrightarrow \iota \leftrightarrow \mu$ such that

⁴Suggestion: One Perception with the sign “look at that guy, what is wrong with him?”, the man acting as the object, and the interpretant “yes, really strange, suddenly he was walking faster and then he started to run.”

⁵Thanks to Susanne Arndt, Torsten Bronger, Marc Fuhrmans, Dorothea Iglezakis, Giacomo Lanza, Taras Petrenko, and Cord Wiljes for discussing the associated schema, *cf.* Fig. 1, within the NFDI4Ing project.

Figure 1. Metadata schema for a Semiosis that is conducted purposefully as a CognitiveAction.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \pi, \iota, \mu \text{ S } \kappa, & \quad \text{the cognition } \kappa \text{ consists of the three steps } \pi, \iota, \text{ and } \mu; \\
 \pi \text{ S}^\perp \kappa, & \quad \text{the observation is the initial step;} \\
 \mu \text{ S}^\top \kappa, & \quad \text{the metonymization (anonymization) is the terminal step,} \quad (17)
 \end{aligned}$$

cf. Fig. 2. For the overall cognitive action, it can be stated that

$$\begin{aligned}
 a \dot{\text{P}}_\iota \kappa, & \quad \text{it is done by the city administration;} \\
 \varphi \text{ R}_\alpha \kappa, & \quad \text{it aims at supporting urban planning;} \\
 \ell' \tilde{\text{R}} \kappa, & \quad \text{the target property is } v(t); \\
 v, t \check{\text{C}} \ell', & \quad \text{velocity and time are constitutive of } v(t); \\
 e, e' \ddot{\text{P}}_{\text{tool}} \kappa, & \quad \text{the camera and the computer are used;} \\
 e, e' \dot{\text{P}}_a, & \quad \text{the city's equipment is considered part of the agent } a. \quad (18)
 \end{aligned}$$

In the first step, a video is recorded such that

$$\begin{aligned}
 s \dot{\text{E}}_{\text{obs}} \pi, & \quad \text{a visual signal is received (as the sign);} \\
 o \ddot{\text{E}}_{\text{obs}} \pi, & \quad \text{the man is observed (as the object);} \\
 s' \ddot{\text{E}}_{\text{obs}} \pi, & \quad \text{a video file is produced (as the interpretant);} \\
 e \ddot{\text{P}}_{\text{tool}} \pi, & \quad \text{the camera is used (as a tool);} \\
 \ell \check{\text{R}} \pi, & \quad \text{the method is } \textit{video recording}. \quad (19)
 \end{aligned}$$

In the second step, the video is processed:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \iota \text{ 3 } (s' \text{ o } s''), & \quad \text{the interpretation } \iota \text{ is given by the triad } s' - o - s''; \\
 e' \ddot{\text{P}}_{\text{tool}} \iota, & \quad \text{the computer is used (as a tool).} \quad (20)
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 2. Sequence of an observation (perception), an interpretation, and a synecdoche (metonymization).

In the final step, we forget whatever we knew about the individual man and anonymize the data set such that it, together with other similar data sets, refers to all the pedestrians:

$$\begin{aligned}
 o \dot{E}_{ptw} \mu, & \quad \text{the man is the old referent of } s''; \\
 s'' \ddot{E}_{ptw} \mu, & \quad \text{the representamen } s'' \text{ undergoes a metonymization;} \\
 o' \ddot{\ddot{E}}_{ptw} \mu, & \quad \text{the pedestrians are collectively the new referent of } s''. \quad (21)
 \end{aligned}$$

We could finally add to this another interpretation, where a city employee inspects the data set and finds that somebody was walking, then accelerating, and finally running.

CASE 4

“A man is walking to the station, but before he gets there, he turns around and goes home.”

The following individuals are needed:⁶

$$\begin{aligned}
 a : \text{Person}, & \quad \text{the man;} \\
 \alpha, \alpha' : \text{Action}, & \quad \text{the actions of going forward and backward, respectively;} \\
 \tau : \text{Steering}, & \quad \text{a steering operation (telesis) for an ongoing action, namely, } \alpha; \\
 \mu : \text{Undertaking}, & \quad \text{the decision to turn around and undertake action } \alpha'; \\
 t : \text{Intention}, & \quad \text{“I would like to go to the station;”} \\
 t' : \text{Intention}, & \quad \text{“This is taking too long, it is about time to go back.”} \quad (22)
 \end{aligned}$$

⁶Notation: \dot{P}_α for isAgentIn, $\dot{\leftrightarrow}_t$ for temporallyPrecedes, $\dot{\leftrightarrow}$ for directlyGrounds, R_α for isAimIn, \dot{E}_{ste} for isTelosInSteering, \ddot{E}_{ste} for isActionInSteering, $\ddot{\ddot{E}}_{ste}$ for isResolutionInSteering, and 3 for isTriadOf. See also <http://www.molmod.info/semantics/pims-ii-examples/benchmark/case-4.ttl> as supplementary material.

Figure 3. Cognitive process from case 4; for various kinds of diagram notations based on Peircean semiotics, cf. previous work [3, Fig. 1], [9, Fig. 5], as well as Sowa [10, Fig. 3] and Chandler [11, p. 34].

The steering operation constitutes a reflection *in actu*.⁷ Concerning the overall process,

$$\begin{aligned}
 a \ddot{P}_\alpha \alpha, \tau, \mu, \alpha', & \quad \text{in walking around and in decision making, the man } a \text{ is the agent;} \\
 \alpha \hookrightarrow_t \alpha', & \quad \alpha \text{ temporally precedes } \alpha'; \\
 \tau \hookrightarrow \mu, & \quad \text{telesis } \tau \text{ directly grounds the decision } \mu \text{ to undertake } \alpha'. \quad (23)
 \end{aligned}$$

The steering process is described by

$$\begin{aligned}
 t R_\alpha \alpha, & \quad \text{walking forward aims at reaching the station;} \\
 t \dot{E}_{\text{ste}} \tau, & \quad t \text{ is the telos (initial objective), } i.e., \text{ the sign;} \\
 \alpha \ddot{E}_{\text{ste}} \tau, & \quad \alpha \text{ is the considered action, } i.e., \text{ the object;} \\
 t' \ddot{E}_{\text{ste}} \tau, & \quad t' \text{ is a new resolution, } i.e., \text{ the interpretant,} \quad (24)
 \end{aligned}$$

cf. Fig. 3, and the decision to go home assigns a new referent to the resolution:

$$\mu \text{ } \mathfrak{3} (\alpha \text{ } t' \text{ } \alpha'), \quad \text{the undertaking } \mu \text{ is given by the triad } \alpha - t' - \alpha'. \quad (25)$$

CASE 5

The original formulation⁸ is rather obscure – let us look at a concrete case where continuity of the meaning of marriage would play a practical role:

At a court hearing, a legal argument is developed as follows: “Law mandates that marriage records be issued by the state, subsequent to a marriage ceremony conducted by the state. Yet it was the church that took care of the formalities in 1860 when Kathrin and Friedrich Mayer were married. Soon after, Friedrich died and the young widow

⁷*Reflexion im Vollzug* following Franke [6], Baumann [7], and Tülatz [8].

⁸“A marriage is a contract that is regulated by civil and social constraints. These constraints can change but the meaning of marriage continues over time” [1].

Figure 4. Cognitive process from case 5.

inherited his property. If they had been unmarried it should have gone to his brother Paul; however, marriages following the customs of the time continue to enjoy legal recognition, and Paul Mayer's descendants cannot claim ownership of the property."

The discussion of the legal validity of the marriage can be formalized as a cognition consisting of two examination processes (perceptions), cf. Fig. 4, where legisigns (*i.e.*, patterns or rules) are applied to documents on the marriage between K. and F. Mayer,⁹

o : Object,	documentation of the marriage;
κ : Cognition,	a cognitive process consisting of two steps;
π, π' : Examination,	two examination processes;
l, l' : Structure,	two legisigns (present law and contemporary practice);
φ : Proposition,	final examination outcome, stating that o is valid,

(26)

such that

$\pi S^\perp \kappa$,	the cognition κ begins with π ;
$\pi' S^\top \kappa$,	the cognition κ ends with π' ;
$\pi \hookrightarrow \pi'$,	π directly grounds π' ;
$o \ddot{E}_{\text{exa}} \pi, \pi'$,	o is the examined object, <i>i.e.</i> , the second triadic element,

(27)

where

$l \dot{E}_{\text{exa}} \pi$,	the marriage is assessed with respect to present law;
$l' \ddot{E}_{\text{exa}} \pi$,	the outcome is that contemporary practice needs to be considered;

⁹Notation: S^\perp for isInitialStepIn, S^\top for isTerminalStepIn, \hookrightarrow for directlyGrounds, \ddot{E}_{exa} for isExaminedIn, \dot{E}_{exa} for isLegisignIn, and \ddot{E}_{exa} for isExaminationOutcomeIn; cf. <http://www.molmod.info/semantics/pims-ii-examples/benchmark/case-5.ttl> as supplementary material.

$$\begin{aligned}
l' \dot{E}_{\text{exa}} \pi', & \quad \text{therefore contemporary practice is taken into account in the second step;} \\
\varphi \ddot{E}_{\text{exa}} \pi', & \quad \text{the marriage is thereby found to be legally valid.} \quad (28)
\end{aligned}$$

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